

IMPACT OF STRESS MANAGEMENT ON ABSENTISM OF DEGREE COLLEGE FACULTIES DURING COVID – 19 – A STUDY AT UDUPI DISTRICT KARNATAKA.

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ABSTRACT

Presently corona virus (Covid -19) has resulted in highest rate of absentism, especially among teaching faculties working at esteemed private colleges. Private colleges expect their teaching staffs to report to their respective duties in regular working hours when the situation is normal. At present due to the outbreak of covid 19 institutions were shut down as government imposed strict lock down across the country. Hence many of the faculties coming from outside couldn't report on time as per the directions of management of private institutions. Normally management want faculties to be in the campus engage online classes & also finish department related works. Due to particular unavoidable reasons most of the faculties couldn't report on time as per institutions management expectations. This paper focuses on absenteeism of teaching faculties due to increased level of stress, its impact and suggested remedies for the same are given to a certain possible extent.

Key words: Absentism, Esteemed, Expected, Unavoidable, stress & Remedies.

INTRODUCTION

One of the important concerns affecting any institution is continuous absence of prominent teaching staffs. Faculties are considered as the real strength of any institution, because they inspire, motivate & enlighten students which will directly result in upliftment of society & building a strong & stable nation. It is said that eminent bodies like NAAC (National accreditation assessment council), IQAC (Internal Quality assurance cell) & LIC (Local inspection committee) are of strong opinion that institutes should be recognized by its faculties & not faculties should be recognized by the institutions where they provide service. Faculties can also bring quality students by their efforts, personal attention & sharing rich knowledge to them which will directly result in building the nation on one side & also contributing substantially for our society which is in desperate need of young talents. Absentism of faculties in institutes may be due to one or more particular reasons; especially the following could be possible to a certain extent;

- 1) Less job satisfaction
- 2) No cordial relationships between the peers

- 3) Poor working conditions
- 4) Poor health & medical grounds
- 5) Maternity problems in female staffs
- 6) Lack of financial benefits & incentives
- 7) Institutional politics
- 8) Favoritism& nepotism
- 9) Lethargic reporting authorities who do not recognize good works.
- 10) No credit for good works
- 11) Long unexpected holidays

Covid-19 as we know has spread faster across the globe this pandemic can affect human lives faster, therefore where there are mass gatherings like institutes had to be shut down for quite a longer period as per the central government directive. Educational institute is one such field where we observe large number of students coming up to pursue their education from different places. Since there is a quick possibility of spreading this disease due to mass gathering, government of India decided to announce complete lock down in the country with effect from 24th March 2020. Even at this moment condition has turned up so much critical that it is not at all possible to open the institutes at present. But still institutions expect their teaching staffs to be present within the institutional campus to carry out all those clerical activities which a faculty as a professional should not carry out. This will neither help the students as well as the growth of faculties. Some of the institutes even are using undue influence on faculties towards deducting their earned leave (EL) which can be encashed after a certain period of their service. Quality teaching, research & publication of articles are given minimum or no weightage. Their major concerns are getting maximum admissions for all courses, filling the seats, putting faculties in all such tasks that shall hamper their professional growth. Hence this has raised major concern with all competent, talented & skillful employees who put their blood & sweat for the upliftment of institutions. These competent faculties discharge their duties on time, perform better in their professions, provide justice to the subject whom they handle & also to their students. This may strongly result in the following.

- 1) Lack of trust towards management.
- 2) Procrastination of duties.
- 3) Delay in completion of regular work.
- 4) Regular person turns irregular in his duty, delay in reporting.
- 5) No active involvement in important tasks.
- 6) Lack of positive thinking.
- 7) Lack of learning & focus towards research.
- 8) Affect professional development.

Faculties are informed to join their duties without considering their genuine problems, without providing them with moral support at this crucial period where the whole world is in danger & facing crisis like situation everywhere. Genuine reasons for absentism may be the following;

- 1) Lock down announced by the government for the protection of human beings as there was no much remedy found at the crucial period.

- 2) Outstation faculties finding difficult to commute from one place to another.
- 3) Lack of transportation facilities.
- 4) Poor health & regulations imposed by health department.
- 5) Problems with district & state level border crossing, this may lead to compulsory quarantine.
- 6) Delays in getting government approved pass.
- 7) Personal reasons

Normal impact of absentism of faculties on institutes:

Faculties while on duty perform their tasks continuously which will bring credit to their institution & also to the society. On the other hand they teach & train students in a well decisive manner so that they can progress & prosper in every walks of their life in their respective professions. Hence faculties remain as facilitators of growth directly for students & indirectly for the institutions. An institution can progress only when their staffs (Teaching faculty) are looked after well & they are satisfied in their profession. The following aspects can be observed in teaching if the faculties are not looked after as per the expected standards.

- 1) Institution may lose its charm, name, fame & reputation.
- 2) Increase in the number of faculty turnovers year on year.
- 3) Faculties with broader & deeper knowledge & quality teaching may not be available to the institutions.
- 4) Affects work climate & working standards miserably.
- 5) Admissions start reducing below the expectations.
- 6) Quality of the students passing out of institute starts deteriorating & they will not be employable in the industry.

Causes for stress among faculties:

When the private management institutes wanted to cut down the costs & who themselves were not aware of the next move decided to take the following steps till the pandemic came down.

1. Salary of the staffs were reduced by 50%.
2. No additional payments. On the other side increased commitments on daily basis.
3. No opportunities available as it was in the earlier normal times.
4. Never ending expectations of management led to increased work burden on faculties.
5. Management wanted to take up most of the clerical assignments by faculties, no additional staff deputed for the same.
6. There was no distinction between personal timings & professional working hours. Management expected staff to work for round the clock.
7. More availability of faculties made management to threaten faculties by opting for easily available replacement of faculties (Cost cutting).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Herrmann and Rockoff (2012) found that the daily loss in student achievement resulting from having a substitute teacher is comparable to replacing an average teacher with one between the 10th and 20th percentile in terms of teaching effectiveness. Other researchers note that providing for substitute teachers incurs heavy financial costs.

Chang (2010) found that absenteeism as missing ten percent of the school year and importantly includes all absences in this count, excused and unexcused. Including all absences is important for very young students in elementary school because it is extremely unlikely that a parent does not know about their child's absence. As children age and move into the secondary school level, truancy is generally defined in terms of unexcused absences and comes with the possibility that parents are unaware of their child's absences.

Maynard (2012) found that the reasons for absenteeism exist, including a number of family risk factors, health reasons, lack of resources, domestic violence, lack of interest or ability on the part of the student and the student's perception of the school, classroom and teacher. One study suggests a number of family risk factors that are an adequate early predictor of student absenteeism: low level of parental education, being born to a teenage mother, living below the poverty index, living in a family with 4 or more children, receiving welfare, having unemployed parents, having a parent with poor health or having food insecurity.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

It is seen & heard that covid-19 has brought huge problem to the whole world because of which complete lock down was announced by the government. This made educational institutes also discontinue their operations for longer periods. Management of private institutes wanted their teaching faculties to be present in the campus & carry out clerical activities other than teaching & research. When we look other side it was seen that many of the faculties who were dedicated in their professions could not attend their duties due to some unavoidable reasons. This had resulted in a gap between management expectations from the faculties & faculties remaining absent in the institutional campus. Management expects returns on investments & considers payments made to the faculty as cost. Hence with this thinking they want faculties to be within the institute & work for the same without looking at the present critical situation the whole world is facing. Instead of expecting them in the campus they can carry out the same work at home & make a periodic reporting to the concerned authorities.

METHODOLOGY USED

Primary data is collected using online questionnaire shared in email & whatsapp to the concerned faculty groups. Even telephonic interview is also made to collect immediate responses from faculties. Secondary data is collected from books, journals, magazines & related sites. Primary data collected from the respondents is further used to carry out indepth analysis using applicable statistical tool.

Type of sampling used in this study is simple random sampling (Convenient sampling). Number of population taken for this study is fifty respondents who are faculties working in premier institutes. These faculties carry good experience in teaching & has a good track record built in

the past. The area chosen for carrying out this study is Udupi & Udupi districts covering both urban & rural areas.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To understand the impact of faculties absentism on institutions.
- 2) To study the relationship between job productivity & faculty absentism.
- 3) To analyze the impact of faculty absentism on institutional practices.
- 4) To give suggestions based on the findings of the study.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. This study is undertaken at Udupi city & Udupi districts only.
2. Only 50 members are taken in this study.
3. Respondents above 55 years are not considered in this study.
4. Only management staffs are taken in this study, aided (Government/UGC) staffs are not taken in this study.
5. Opinions are given directly by the targeted audience; hence there may be biases in the responses observed. But however, to the level best it is tried to minimize bias responses.
6. Certain opinion provided by faculties could not be disclosed because of confidentiality.

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1: Age of respondents

Age in (Years)	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
25 – 35	13	26
35 – 45	25	50
45 – 55	12	24
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Table 2: Designation of faculties

Designation	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Assistant professor	34	68
Associate Professor	16	32
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Table 3: Length of expenditures (in years)

Experience (in years)	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
<10	16	32
10 – 15	18	36
>15	16	32
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Table 4: Gender of respondents

Gender	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	24	48
Female	26	52
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Table 5: Normal expectations from management

Expenditure	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Stock verification	10	20
E – Lectures	12	2
Departmental work	15	30
Clerical work	13	26
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Table 6: Opinion on work productivity of faculties

Productivity	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Decreases	22	44
Remains same	28	56
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Table 7: Time of absentism

Time of absentism	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Less than one week	18	36
1 – 2 week	17	34
Above 2 weeks	15	30
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Table 8: Management action for absentism

Action taken	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Consider earned leave (EL)	23	46
Loss of pay (LOP)	27	54
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Chi square test

Chi square test is a non-parametric test which is used in this study to determine the degree association two variables. Calculated value of this test is given by:

$$\sum \frac{(fo - fe)^2}{fe}$$

Where ‘fo’ is observed frequency and ‘fe’ is expected frequency

Expected frequency is given by

(Row total X Column total)/ Gross total

After expected frequency is calculated the difference between observed and expected frequencies are made which is then squared and then divided by expected frequency. This will give the value of calculated chi square.

Tabulated value of chi square is taken from chi square table. This is done by taking selected

confidence interval limit and calculating degrees of freedom using $(r-1)(c-1)$ where 'r' is the number of rows and 'c' is for number of columns. If chi square calculated is greater than chi square tabulated null hypothesis is rejected else accepted.

- 1) **H₀: Time period of absentism and work productivity are independent of each other.**
H₁: Time period of absentism and work productivity are not independent of each other.

Work productivity	Time period of absentism			Total
	Less than a week	1 – 2 weeks	Above 2 weeks	
Decreases	06	07	09	22
Remains same	12	10	06	28
Total	18	17	15	50

Chi square calculated value is 2.4445 and the table value at 5% level of significance at degrees of freedom 2 is 5.991. Hence table value is higher than calculated value, we therefore accept null hypothesis.

- 2) **H₀: Gender and time period of absentism are independent of each other.**
H₁: Gender and time period of absentism are not independent of each other.

Gender	Time period of absentism			Total
	Less than a week	1 – 2 weeks	Above 2 weeks	
Male	10	08	06	24
Female	08	09	09	26
Total	18	17	15	50

Chi square calculated value is 0.8835 and the table value at 5% level of significance at degrees of freedom 2 is 5.991. Hence table value is higher than calculated value, we therefore accept null hypothesis.

MAJOR FINDINGS

- 1) Respondents in the age group of 35- 45 years are higher in number(Table 1).
- 2) 68%of the respondents are assistant professors & the rest 32% respondents are associate professors carrying rich experience & appointed by the management of the institute (Table 2).
- 3) 36% of the respondents carry 10 to 15years of experience, 32% have less than 10 years of experience& the rest 32% have experience of above 15 years (Table 3).
- 4) 52% of the respondents arefemales & the rest 48% are males (table4).
- 5) 44% of the respondents say that work productivity decreases due to absentism and 56% say that work productivity remains same (Table6).
- 6) 36% of the respondents are absent for less than a week, 34% are absent for one to two weeks & the rest 30% are absent for more than two week (Table 7).
- 7) Time period of absentism & work productivityof absentees are independent of each other (Chi Square 1).
- 8) Gender of faculties & the time period of absentism are independent of each other (Chi Square 2).

MAJOR SUGGESTIONS

- 1) Management of concerned institutes should direct the principals of their college to deal with faculties liberally at this moment as this situationisvery critical to the world itself.
- 2) Faculties morale should not be brought down & they should not be made to feel isolated because this may hamper their future academic performance.

- 3) Faculties salary should not be deducted at any cost.
- 4) Management can plan for staff rotation schedule so that absentism can be reduced.
- 5) Senior staffs above 50 years should be provided more relaxations considering their age & health conditions.
- 6) Those faculties who are coming from other districts, states etc. has border issues so they must be exempted from reporting to the duties until the situation returns back to normal.

CONCLUSION

Regular absentism is totally different from absentism experienced during the outbreak of covid-19. Here faculties working for private institutes may remain away from duty due to one or other valid & genuine reasons. It is better that management of institutes deal with such faculties humbly showing a great sign of concern, understanding problems of faculty, educating them more & more about health & safety rules, making work place more & more safe & less risky. From the institutions point of view, it is always better that employee (faculties) to be treated as human capital itself than any kind of unproductive resources.

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